

The Potential of Fungal Biomass as Agents for Biosorption of Chromium (VI) Ion from Tannery Effluent

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Abstract

Biosorption and bioaccumulation are the overall process by which microorganism tolerate toxic levels of heavy metals in the environment. Thus, filamentous fungi are able to accumulate significant amount of metals from their environment. The potential of fungal biomass as agents for biosorption of chromium (VI) ion from tannery effluent is currently receiving attention. In the present study a total of four isolate of filamentous fungi and *Candida* sp, were obtained from tannery effluent Mario Jose locate at Challawa industrial estate Kano. These fungi were characterized morphologically, microscopically and screened for their tolerance and uptake capability of chromium (VI) ion in medium. The isolates were identified as viz; *Rhizopus nigricans* *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium* sp. Only three of these species were able to survived at 4% concentration of chromium ion solution on modified rice husk medium (MRHM). The results showed that *Rhizopus nigricans* and *Aspergillus niger* have better uptake capacity for chromium (VI) ion by these filamentous fungi from aqueous solution. The present study was also determined the maximum removal of chromium (VI) ion that performed by *Rhizopus nigricans*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium* sp and mixed culture organisms. The chromium (VI) removal with initial concentration ranging from 1.517mg/l – 0.067, 1.517mg/l – 0.072mg/l and *Penicillium* sp 1.517mg/l – 0.73mg/l and mixed culture 1.517mg/l – 0.874mg/l. The above studies show *Rhizopus nigricans* and *Aspergillus niger* organisms appear to be more

effective in biosorption of Cr^{6+} in effluent using modified agricultural waste in comparison with conventional one's base on time duration of absorption.

Keywords: *Chromium (VI), Tolerance fungi, Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS), 1,5 diphenylcarbazides, Physicochemical parameters, Ligands, Metal binding capacity.*

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Introduction

The discharge of chromium (VI) into aquatic ecosystem has become a matter of concern in all the tanneries areas in Kano State Nigeria over the last few decades. This pollutant is introduced into the aquatic system significantly from effluent of leather processing units as a result of chrome tanning of leather (Pagnanelli et al., 2002). Heavy metals released into the environment are found to increase continuously as an impact from industrial activities and technological development. It possesses significant threat to the environment, public and soil (Zafar et al., 2007). Due to their application and immutable nature increased recently, heavy metal pollution has naturally become one of the serious environmental problems. Tannery industries release effluents directly on the agricultural land or surface of water bodies which eventually leaches to ground water that lead to contamination of toxic metallic component and result in a sense of well documented problem in living beings (Zang and Li., 2011). Chromium exists in many oxidation states of which only Cr (VI) and Cr (III) ions are the most stable under environmental circumstances (Masood and Malik, 2011). Chromium (III) is required in human body, but in very small amounts and relatively immobile, slightly acidic to alkaline and chemically more stable than Cr (VI) and less bio available due to its negligibility and permeable nature to bio membrane. Cr (VI) is highly mobile and water soluble when compare to Cr (III), whereas chromium is also used as a pigment. Hexavalent chromium can be harmful to human health and is toxic, mutagenic and also carcinogenic (APHA et al., 1998). Chromates in soils have also been found to induce allergic reactions in some individuals. Due to those health and environmental issues, restrictions have been imposed on the use of certain chromium compounds in many countries. Conventional method for removing Cr^{6+} from aqueous solution has been studied in detailed such as chemistry precipitation ion exchange, electrochemical treatment of membrane technologies. However, these methods are ineffective and uneconomical (Wong and Chen, 2006). Therefore, rapid and economical design technologies are needed to develop by mean of heavy metals removal from industrials effluent.

Research Problem

Heavy metals persist in soil and can be adsorbed in soil particles or leached into ground water. Human exposure to these metals through ingestion of contaminated food or uptake of drinking water can lead to their accumulation in humans, animals and plants (Khan, 2006). Recent research suggests that heavy metals induce tumor and mutation in animals at high concentrations (Degraeve, 1981). They are capable of causing genetic damage to germ cells of male and female animals including humans. They are regarded as cumulative toxins which through biomagnification in plants affect human health (Groten and Vanbladeren, 1994). Wastes containing heavy metals are usually disposed in landfills and streams in Kano. These streams are used in irrigation for the production of agricultural products (Carrots and vegetables) which in turn may cause ill health (cancer) to humans and also render the land devastated and

unproductive for Agricultural activities (Gbolagunte et al., 2003). Proper treatment of this waste is extremely essential for the public to use this waste water for irrigation and other purposes.

Figure 1. Accumulated Chromium Ion Spotted on Fungal by Product of *Rhizopus nigricans* after 45 Days Incubation (Lipoproteins)

Justification of the Research

Uncontrolled discharge of industrial effluent causes pollution of water by certain heavy metal ions and consumption of such contaminated water may lead to severe health problem. The metal ions may enter the food chain and become toxics in view of their high toxicity, environmental mobility, non-biodegradability and stability, their removal becomes an absolute necessity.

In recent years biosorption of heavy metals by microbial cells have been recognized as a potential alternative to the existing technologies for removing heavy metal from industrial effluent and accumulation of metals by microorganisms or their products have received attention as the metal ion concentration lower than 10 mg/l can thus be removed (Vasudevas *et al.*, 2002).

Furthermore, in view of the increasing cost of using the existing technologies for bioremediation, using available agricultural waste materials is increasingly being considered. Thus, the use of modified rice husk, soya bean pod, ground/nut pod, and saw dust as materials for substitution of expensive, not easily available basal media is quite essential.

The results of this research project will highlight the significance of bioremediation using media containing locally available wastes as an efficient means of removing toxic metals present in tannery effluent.

Figure 2a. Picture Showing Growth Tolerant of *Aspergillus niger* after Exposure to Different concentration CrSO_4 at A=0.0%; B=0.1%; C=0.5%, D=2%; E=4%

Figure 2b. Picture Showing Growth Tolerant of *Penicillium sp* after Exposure to Different Concentration CrSO_4 at A=0.0%; B=0.1%

Research Aim and Objectives

The main purpose of this study is to assess the detoxification of Cr (VI) from tannery effluent in Kano state of Nigeria by using microorganisms isolated from the effluent and agricultural waste materials.

The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. To Isolate and identify different fungi from tannery effluent and contaminated soil
2. To compare the growth of fungi isolated from contaminated soil and tannery effluent on both conventional and dried modified agricultural waste media
3. To determine the maximum tolerance level of these isolated fungi on different chromium salt concentrations using different media
4. To formulate and compare the efficient use of dried modified agricultural waste as alternative media for growth of microorganisms for treatment of tannery effluent waste in solid state fermentation.
5. To establish a concession of using 1,5 diphenyl carbazide to justified the binding metal capacity of (Cr^{6+})/ hexavalent is satisfactorily and adequately justified its norm
6. To determine chromium ions (Cr^{3+} & Cr^{4+})/total chromium using AAS (Atomic spectrometer) for the detection level of chromium discharge both on land and stream abatement by absorbance capacity
7. To evaluate findings of tannery effluent using physicochemical analyses like those of chromium ions, pH, temperature, Mg, Fe, Cu etc respectively.
8. Determination of tolerance fungal isolates to chromium sulphate salt.

Research Questions

Does bio-absorption of tannery effluent containing Cr^{6+} by filamentous fungi justifiable?

Is tannery effluent discharge on landfill abatement affect animals and human's health?

Why is it that Cr^{6+} (Hexavalent) is so carcinogenic, teratogenic and mutagenic those of Cr^{4+} and Cr^{3+} /total chromium?

Why is it that Cr^{3+} in virgin soil so friendly to microorganisms and humans at low concentration in comparison to tannery effluent discharged on land fill abatement?

Significance of the Study

So far so good, increased attention has focused on the use of microorganisms for the removal and possible recovery of metal ions from industrial wastes. As matter of truth, it represents a potential alternative to existing technologies (chemical precipitation, reverse osmosis, solvent extraction), which have significant disadvantages such as high reagent or energy requirements and generation of toxic sludge or other products that need disposal. Biosorption, the passive binding of metals by living or dead biomass, can be used to remove toxic heavy metals from industrial wastewater. Chromium and its compounds are ubiquitous and persistent environmental contaminants released into natural environment from a variety of anthropogenic sources, including the electroplating, leather tanning processes, chromite ore processing, wood preservation, alloys making, corrosion control, pigment, dyes, and metal finishing industries. Though the removal of Cr from wastewater is obligatory before discharging into aquatic environment, the rest in the effluent will still cause serious environmental impact. Therefore, the discharge of Cr into aquatic ecosystems has become a matter of concern over the last few decades. In view of this current investigation, locally available materials were employed to foreseeing processes through which liquidly fruiting bodies /spore of fungi isolates sample plus modified locally process suitable medium; alongside with an appreciable amount of tannery effluent containing chromium ion is set for fermentation. Thus at 45 days using solid state fermentation to possibly recovered metal ions from industrial wastes or tannery effluent.

Literature Review

Environmental pollution has become a major concern of developing countries in the last few decades. There is a growing sense of global urgency regarding the pollution of our environment by an array of chemicals used in various activities. Pollution of water and soil by heavy metals is an emerging problem in urban industrialized countries. Since the advent of development through mining and smelting, metallurgical industries, sewage, warfare, and tanning the survival of plants and animals are much affected (Ashraf, 2010).

The quality of life on earth is inextricably linked to overall quality in the environment. Currently there are two fundamental pollution related problems, the disposal of large quantities of wastes that are continually being produced and the removal of toxic compounds that have been accumulating at dump sites in the soil and in water system over the last few decades (Huppert and Sparks, 2006).

Figure 3. Picture Showing Growth of Pure Cultures of Tolerant *Filamentous sp*
A = *Rhizopus nigricans*; B = *Penicillium sp*; C = *Aspergillus niger* and D = *Aspergillus flavus*

Pollution is defined in various ways. It is considered as the release of unwanted substances to the environment by man in quantities that damage either the health or the resource itself. Environmental pollution caused by heavy metals is increasing along with the increase in the usage of chemicals in industry and agriculture. Such pollution is apparent in streams and lakes and in ground water which is replenished directly from surface water (Schell et al., 2006).

Industrialization

Since the beginning of the industrial revolution, pollution of the biosphere with toxic metals has accelerated dramatically. Increasing industrialization and population develops the standard of living, which results in highly contaminated atmosphere due to the drainage and wastage from these industries (Indus, 2007).

Rapid industrialization plays an important role in polluting the environment and causes severe degradation in pedosphere, hydrosphere and atmosphere. Water used in industries creates a waste that has potential hazard for our environment because of the introduction of various contaminants such as heavy metals into soil and water resources (Rajamani et al., 1987).

Environmental contamination with metals through industrial wastes is one of the major health concerns of developing countries. Metal pollutants can easily enter the food chain if heavy metals contaminated soils are used for the production of crops. The accumulation of metals in an aquatic environment has direct consequences to man and ecosystem (Ahluwalia and Goyal, 2007)).

The release of pollutants differs from industry to industry. The waste from the pulp industry mainly contain carbohydrates, textile industry contains dyes, plating industry contain nickel and leather tanning wastes contain mainly chromium, zinc, copper, sulphides, carbonates, sodium and many other toxic organic compounds and inorganic compounds.

Tannery Effluent

The damage to the environment by the hazardous tannery effluent is an acute problem. The chrome tanning process results in toxic metals, especially chromium III passing to waste water and are not easily eliminated by ordinary treatment process. Tannery waste waters are mainly characterized by high salinity, high organic loading and specific pollutants such as chromium (Shrank et al., 2003).

Various chemicals used in tanning are lime, sodium carbonate, sodium bicarbonate, common salt, sodium sulphate, chrome sulphate, fat liquors, vegetable oils and dyes. The tannery waste water contains high concentrations of total dissolved solids, chromium, chloride, ammonia, nitrate and sulphates when the samples were collected from the outlets of the industry (Song et al., 2004). Besides these, chemicals such as zinc chloride, mercuric chloride and formaldehyde are used as disinfectants, sodium chloride in curing and as bleaching powder and sodium fluoride to prevent putrefaction, lime in liming, sodium sulphate, ammonium chloride, borax and hydrochloric acid in deliming, sodium for decreasing and basic or acidic dyes in leather finishing (Indus, 2006).

Tannery waste is always characterized by its strong colour (reddish dull brown), high BOD, high pH, and high dissolved solids. The other major chemical constituents of the waste from the tanning industry are sulphide and chromium. These chemicals mixed with water are discharged from the tanneries into polluted ground water permanently and thereby making it unfit for drinking, irrigation and general consumption.

Heavy Metals (Chromium)

Plants require certain elements for their normal growth, which are called essential elements (micro and macro elements). But there are also some elements which are not vital for plant growth. Such elements

are called non-essential elements, which include heavy metals which cause toxicity to plants (Leta et al., 2004).

The contamination of the environment with heavy metals is a serious problem. Industrial activities and sewage sludge applications have largely contributed to the spread of these elements in the terrestrial environment (Leta et al., 2004). Heavy metals are ubiquitous environmental contaminants in an industrialized society. Concern over the possible health and ecosystem effects of heavy metals has increased in recent years (Indus, 2006). Tremendous increase in the use of heavy metals over the past decades has inevitably resulted in an increased flux of metallic substances in the environment. Some metallic ions accumulate poisonous substances that is capable of being assimilated and stored in the tissues of organisms causing noticeable adverse physiological effects (UNIDO, 2000).

The most commonly occurring metals at the discharge sites are lead, chromium, arsenic, zinc, cadmium, copper, and mercury. Presence of these metals in the water and soil may cause serious threat to human health and ecological systems. Problems of pollution by metals have aggravated and affected the ecological balance and caused serious health hazards because of the release on land as well as dumping on the surface water. Ultimately metallic components leach to ground water and lead to contamination due to accumulation and results in a series of well documented problems in living things (Mohanta et al., 2010).

Heavy metals used in various industrial activities find their way into the physiological system of the living being. Exposure to heavy metals results in acute and chronic toxicity. The functions of kidney, liver and lungs are mainly affected by these metals

Effect of Tannery Effluent on Soil

The tannery effluents have an undesirable effect on soil properties while the total porosity and hydraulic conductivity of soil decreases are as a result of the addition of effluent, the bulk density of soil increases. This may be attributed to the dual effect of direct accumulation of large quantities of organic and inorganic materials as well as the interaction of Na with exchange complex, which causes deflocculating (Kumar, 2007). The soil treated with tannery effluent was found to be rich in Mg, Mn, Fe, Na and K. The pollution of soil by arsenic contained in tannery waste has also been reported. The addition of tannery effluent is reported to have desirable effect on soil properties. The total porosity and hydraulics of the soil decrease as a result of addition of effluent, while bulk density of soil increased. Sewage sludge from industrial units plays appreciable roles in soil contamination are in toxicities of heavy metals. A majority of heavy metals including chromium are in sulphide residue form in the sewage sludge amended part in making some soils infertile, a heavy dressing of lime reduces toxicity to plants grown in soils that have been treated with chromium, containing tanning wastes. A higher percentage of chromium content was found in infertile soil derived from rock (Nandy et al., 1999).

Effect of Effluent on Plant Growth

Effect of toxic chemicals on plants and environmental impact of tannery effluents on plant and animal kingdom has been extensively studied. The phytotoxic impact of the heavy metal was observed on crop such as cabbage, water chestnut, tomatoes, chilies and rice (Mahontar el at., 2010). Repeated metal exposure of plants affects its physiological processes such as photosynthesis, water relations and mineral nutrition (Das et al., 2006). The impact of toxicity was evident as visible symptoms of chlorosis, yellowing and immature fall of leaves, poor growth and retarded flower, fruit and green yields. Metabolic alterations by metal exposure have also been described in plants either by direct effect on enzymes or other metabolites. This was possibly attributed to the imbalance of nutrients and nutritional disorders in the plants due to metal interactions with plant nutrients. Metallic ions play an important role in the antioxidant network of plants grown with industrial effluents. Metal alterations by heavy metal exposure

also have been described in plants either by a direct effect on enzymes or other metabolites or by its ability to generate reactive oxygen species which may cause oxidative stress (Shanker et al., 2007).

Figure 4. Accumulated Chromium Ion Spotted on Fungal By-Product of *Aspergillus niger* after 45 Days Incubation (Lipoproteins)

Effect of Effluent on Human Health

Industrial hazardous waste may show effects in terms of death and morbidity. This may manifest as respiratory diseases, skin reactions, allergies, diminution of vision, corneal opacity, abortion, malformation of pregnancy, stunted growth, neurological disorders, mental depression, psychiatric changes, altered immune response, chromosomal aberrations and cancer (Kumar, 2007). Health related studies have shown that excessive intake of toxic trace metals results in neurological and cardiovascular diseases as well as renal dysfunction. Hepatitis, cholera, dysentery and typhoid are the most common diseases, which affects large population. The microbial flora of tannery wastes was relatively rich with the organisms such as bacteria, yeast, algae, protozoa and fungi causing irritation and corrosion of the skin and respiratory tract. Hexavalent chromium is toxic and mutagenic to most organisms as well as lung carcinoma in humans. The exposure of metals like chromium, pentachlorophenol and other toxic pollutants increases the risk of dermatitis, ulcer, nasal septum, perforation and lung cancer (Kumar, 2007).

Materials and Methods

Tannery effluent was collected from leather tannery at Mario Jose Kano state of Nigeria. The sample was stored at 4°C to arrest any biological activity. The color and pH of the effluent was recorded. The chrome water obtained from the tannery was filtered using what man's No1 filter paper and pH was adjusted using concentrated HNO₃. The collected tannery effluent was analyzed. Total chromium and hexavalent chromium (VI) using (AAS) (Dexari and Green, 1995). Including the oxidation of trivalent chromium colour development by adding diphenyl carbazides, its measurement of optical density at 540nm using reagents water as reference. The value was plotted against the standard graph to determine the concentration of Cr⁶⁺ in the effluent.

Physicochemical Properties of Tannery Effluent Colour

1.246g of potassium chloroplatinate (K₂ptCl) (equivalent to 500mg metallic Pt) and 1g crystallized cobaltous chloride, COCl₂. 6H₂O (equivalent to about 250mg metallic CO) was dissolved in distilled water containing 100ml of con HCl. The solution was then diluted to 1000ml of distilled water to make

a stock solution (standard) in comparison with the color of 500 units. Standard calibration curve color was prepared in 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 60 and 70 by diluting 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 6.0 and 7.0ml the stock color was standardized with distilled water to 500ml in Nessler tubes. The observed sample color was matched fill with Nessler tube to 50ml mark sample and was standardized in –situ.

Calculation:

$$\text{Colour units} = \frac{A \cdot 50}{B} \quad (1)$$

Where:

A= Estimated color of a diluted sample;

B= ML sample taken for dilution (Nag, 2007)

Turbidity

Twenty-five ml of water sample was thoroughly shaken and pause for a while until air bubbles disappear. The sample was then poured into turbid meter tube and the turbidity was read directly from the instrument scale or from appropriate calibration curves i.e. Measurement of turbidities less than 40 NTU.

Twenty-five ml of water sample was diluted with one or more volumes of turbidity free water until turbidity falls between 30 and 40 NTU. The original sample was compared from the turbidity of diluted sample and the dilution factor i.e. Measurement of turbidities above 40 NTU.

Calculation:

$$\text{Nephelometric turbidity units (NTU)} = \frac{A \cdot [A \cdot (B + C)]}{C} \quad (2)$$

Where:

A= NTU found in diluted sample

B= Volume of dilution water in ml

C= Sample volume taken for dilution in ml (Nag, 2007).

pH

Twenty-five and of the effluent waste was pipette into 50 ml of a beaker, the effluent waste was then filtered through nylon cloth and suspended particles was then allowed to stand for one hour before using the electrode in the clamps of the electrode holder down into the beaker. The glass electrode was immersed just deep enough into the clear supernatant solution to establish a good electrical contact through the ground glass and was read on the pH (Nag,2007).

Temperature

Ten grams of soil sample was taken and added to 25ml of distilled water and then the mixture was agitated thoroughly for 20 minutes. The temperature was determined using the thermometer in solution (Aneja, 2007).

Total Chromium

Fifty gram of the dried crushed soil was suspended in 50ml distilled water in a beaker and was filtered through nylon cloth. Twenty five of the filtrate was collected in a 400ml beaker and 10ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 and 5ml of concentrated HNO_3 were added to the filtrate in ratio 3/1. The beaker containing the mixture was then placed on a hot plate for boiling until the solution becomes clear and then the solution was transferred by filtration through what man Filter paper No2 into a volumetric flask. The volume of the filtrate was made up to 50ml by adding deionised water. Digested sample were store in sterile polyethylene bottles at room temperature for further analysis of the metal using Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry, FAAS (Rani, 2003).

Figure 5. Picture Showing Mixed Culture of *Aspergillus niger* and Some *Candida sp.* Isolated from Mario Jose Tannery Kano Using Home Base Medium

Fungal Isolation

10ml of effluent waste suspension was pipette into 90ml water blank number 2 to make up 1:100 (10^{-2}) and another 10ml of the effluent suspension was pipette into 90ml water blank number 3 to make up make up 1:1000(10^{-3}). Furthermore, dilutions were repeated carried out for 10^{-4} to 10^{-7} respectively. 0.1ml aliquot was aseptically transferred into freshly prepared potato dextrose agar medium. The plates were then incubated at ambient temperature (27 – 32°C) for 3-4 days emerged fungal colonies were packed and aseptically subculture. Into freshly prepared PDA and incubated in obtain a pure isolate.

All the colonies prepared on each plate were marked, the colony forming unit (CFU) was calculated and subculture into potato dextrose agar PDA slants and kept at 4°C until required for further studies (Adawiah, 2008).

Fungi Identification by Morphological Characteristic (Macroscopic) and Microscopic Observation

Fungal colonies appeared in plate for enumeration of fungal micro flora in effluent discharge was further painted by sub culturing number of times on modified Rice husk agar (MRHN) plates.

Determination of Tolerance Fungal Isolates to Chromium Sulphate Salt

The resistance of fungal isolates to chromium was determines by among the fungi on modified Rice Husk Agar (MRHA) containing different concentration (0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2 and 4%) of chromium, mycelia length was measured and recoded.

Treatment of Agricultural Waste (Saw Dust and Rice Husk)

Agriculture waste either saw dust or rice husk was procured, from Sabon Gari Market, Zaria and brought to the Laboratory for analysis. The waste was re-grounded and sieved to obtain a fine texture. Two hundred and fifty grams of fine texture was weighed and added to 1000 ml of basal media with the following composition (g/l): NH_4SO_4 - 1.0; $\text{K}_2\text{HP0}_4$ 1.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -1.0; CaCO_3 - 4.0; Nacl-1.0 and NaN0_3 - 6.0; $\text{K}_2\text{HP0}_4$ - 2.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 0.20. The mixture was then mixed and boiled to semi-solid slurry after which a prepared solution of two hundred and fifty grams of yellow purple *Parkia biglobosa* (Dorowa) was added and boiled to breakdown the complex organic compound to simpler substances. The paste slurry was later spread on a dried sterile tray and oven dried at 40°C for 7 days. The pH of the paste slurry was brought down using *Tamarindu indica* (Tsamia) from 3.5 - 4.5 and was dried for further analysis.

Figure 6. Accumulated Chromium Ion Spotted on Fungal by-Product of *Penicillium* sp. after 45 Days Incubation (Lipoproteins/Biomass)

Biosorption Studies Using Selected Fungi

The absorptive capacities of three fungi species, simply and in combination was studied. Using the modified method of (Habiba 2006), the organisms used were namely *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus nigricans*, *Penicillium* sp and a mixed culture. 20g of the modified rice husk medium was added to each different volume (50, 65, 75, 85, and 100 ml) of tannery effluent to 5.2 and sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes. The solution was allowed to cool after the inoculums of fungi cell suspension was prepared by adding 5ml of sterile distilled water to freshly grown mycelia in slant agar bottle four ml of spore suspension containing *Aspergillus niger* was added. The conical flasks were then incubated specifically for (0, 15, 30, and 45 days) at (32°C). The entire sample was at specific interval using what man filter paper No4. The filtrate or the supernatant liquid obtained after removed of mycelia mat was used for Cr (VI) ions analyzed.

Determination of Chromium (VI) content of Remediated Effluent Principle: solution chromium (VI) is leached from the sample at 7.5 to 8.0 under inert gas the chromium (VI) in solution oxidizes 1, 5 diphenylcarbazides to 1, 5 diphenylcarbazone to give a red/ violet complex with chromium which is quantities photometrically at 540 nm chemicals

Diphenylcarbazides solution: 1.0g of 1, 5 diphenylcarbazides CO (NHNHC₆H₅)₂ was dissolved in 100 ml acetone (CH₃)₂CO and made acidic with one drop of glacial acetic CH₃COOH. This was kept in brown glass bottle. The shelf life up to 14 days at 4 ° C

Chromium (VI) stock solution: 2.829 g potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) dried for 16 hours at $102^\circ C$ was dissolved in water in a volumetric flask and made up to 1000 ml with water. 1 ml of this solution contains 1 mg of chromium:

Chromium (VI) standard solution: 1 mg of solution was pipette in to the mark with distilled water. 1 ml of this solution contains μg chromium.

Procedure

Ten ml of this supernatant liquid was pipette into a 50 ml volumetric flask. The solution was diluted with water; one ml of diphenylcarbazides solution was added followed by one ml phosphoric acid with distilled water, after ten minute the pink colouration solution was analyzed for Cr (VI) ions using spectrometer at absorbance of 540 nm against the black solution. Another ten ml aliquot of the solution was pipette into a 50 ml volumetric flask and treated as described above but without the addition of the diphenylcarbazide solution.

The blank solution was prepared by filling 50 ml distilled water. Then one ml of diphenylcarbazides solution and 1 ml of phosphoric acid were added to made up the mixed throughout and was stored in a dark and cool place. The calibrating solutions are prepared in 50 ml volumetric flask. A suitable calibration curves standards containing 0.1,0.2,0.3,0.4,0.5,1,1.5,2.5,and $3\mu g$ Cr were taken and acidized with 0.2N of 5 ml of 1,5 - diphenyl carbazides was added 10 ml treated sample until a pink colored was develop and the absorbance measurement was performed at 540nm with spectrophotometric data of calibration standards (Addis, 2006).

Results and Discussion

Soil is an important sub – system of the terrestrials’ ecosystem. The direct discussion of industrial effluents, especially without treatment to soil may affect its biological properties. In the present study, discharge of effluent from tannery industry affects microbial population in soil. Hence, the characteristics of fungal species base on their morphology and tolerant level of chromium solution is absolutely necessary.

Metal tolerance by microbes generally assumed that exposure to metals leads to the establishment of a tolerant microbial population. Microbial tolerance is defined as the ability of microorganisms to survived metals toxicity by means of intrinsic properties and or environmental modification of toxicity (Rajiv et al, 2009).

The morphological and microscopic characteristics of fungal cultures isolated from tannery effluent are listed in Table1 and plate 2a, 2b,4,6. On the basis of a comparison of these of these characteristics were recorded. Five fungal isolates identified were viz; *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus nigricans*, *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida* sp.

Tolerance test conducted for the various fungi isolated from tannery effluent reveal that *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus nigricans* and *Penicillium* sp tolerated chromium concentration solution up to 4% as shown in table 2. While plate 2a, 2b showed the growth tolerant of respective pure culture. Fungi have greater potential for remediation by virtue of their aggressive growth, greater biomass production and extensive physical reach in soil. Several research result of studies on tolerances ability of *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium* sp and *Fusarium* sp to heavy metal Cr, Zn, Ni, Pb, and Ca (Gaddy 1990). A study reported by Prince and Classan,(2001) showed that, *Aspergillus* grows better or tolerated heavy metals compared to other fungi. The results of the present investigation showed that *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus nigricans* and *Penicillium* sp were more tolerance to high concentration of chromium. This is in line with these facts, the variation in the chromium ions tolerance might the attributed to the presence strategies or resistance mechanism

exhibited by different fungi. Tolerance of toxic metals is based on ionic species associating with the surface or extra cellular polysaccharides protein and chitin (volesky, 1990).

In general, potential microorganism especially fungi species can remove heavy metals from solution by biosorption or bio accumulation solution by bacterial fungi ciliates Moses algae and higher plants (Rachan et al., 2008). Three selected filamentous fungi viz; *Rhizopus nigricans*, *aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium* sp showed considerable decreases in biosorption of chromium (VI) ion with increases in days of incubation ranging (0 – 45days). The highest absorption rate was observed by *Rhizopus nigricans* (0.067) mg/l at the efficiency of 94.20% followed by *Aspergillus niger* (0.073 mg/l) at the efficiency of 88.45% as shown in table 3, 4 and 5. While plate 3 and 4 were fungi biomass after 45days incubator. These finding is in agreement with the study conducted by Romomanko and Koren (1977). Hence, both fungi not only exhibited the ability to survive in contaminated waste water but also demonstrated a marked increase in remediation to toxic Cr (VI) in contaminated effluent of the chromium tannery yard (Ganguli and Tripath 2002). One potential method is microbially catalyzed reduction of Cr (VI) by *Aspergillus* sp which was first reported with (Remmananko and Kuren, 1977).

Chromium, a heavy metal was detected to be 1.517mg/l from the initial concentration which is being discharge into the landfill at this low chrome concentration and it does not comply with the WHO standard of 0.05mg/l. In this current investigation, it was found that *Rhizopus nigricans* (0.067) mg/l at the efficiency of 94.20% followed by *Aspergillus niger* (0.073 mg/l) at the efficiency of 88.45%. A possible explanation for its low level above 0.05mg/l is the use of chromium salt during tanning. This could be disastrous to the concept of a clean environment. It may also enter the food chain through plants, animals as well as water source. Once it gets into food chains, biomagnifications and bioaccumulation of the metal in various living systems may take place. This result was in conformity with that of Khan (2006), who reported that bioaccumulation and biomagnifications could lead to toxic level of these metals in organism even, if exposure level is low. This could also cause disruption in the ecological balance when in abundance. However, the said permissible limit for total chromium discharge in the stream or river for irrigation and domestic used should not exceed 0.05 mg/l WHO (2004). Then, the rural dwellers that leave within that vicinity are not guarantee of safety. High concentration of chromium ion in drinking water can cause skin, allergic reactions, carcinogenic and mutagenic allergic effect to humans (Martin and Griswold, 2009).

In this present investigation, the possible mechanism of hexavalent chromium reduction by filamentous fungi isolated from tannery waste by biosorption studies has been evaluated *Rhizopus* ability to reduce hexavalent chromium ranging from initial concentration (1.517- 0.067mg/l) and (1.517 – 0.07mg/l) respectively. Hence both the isolates have been their usefulness in removing chromium (VI) ion from tannery effluent. The technology when upgraded will be a booster to tanneries in talking the pollution problems of tannery waste. The process would not only be economical but also eco-friendly and sustainable.

The mechanism of removal of chromium (VI) ion from the solution by fungi could be attributed to the fact that microbes responsible in biosorption are largely involved physical adsorption followed by chemical bondage and does not required energy once the metals ions are diffused on the cell surface they bind to sites which exhibit chemical affinity for the metal. It is a passive accumulation process, which may include adsorption, ion exchange, complexation, chelation, and micro precipitation. Such physiological study includes the following (Carboxylic, hydroxyl and phosphate group of lipids, protein polysaccharides localized at the cell surface for maximum adsorption (Preetha and Viruthagiri, 2005).

Changes in pH due to chromium biosorption are shown in table 3, 4 and 5 shows a gradual increase in pH of the medium during Cr (VI) biosorption studies by fungal isolates on media containing agricultural waste MRHM and MSDM. The pH changed from 5.20 on the 1st day to between (7.20-7.80) on day 45 of biosorption in effluent Mario-Jose tannery. In contrast, the pH of effluent undergoing Cr (VI)

biosorption in PDM showed a decrease from 5.20 day 1 to pH 4.0 -4.6 on day 45 of incubation. pH is one of the most important physical parameters that influence biosorption and activity microbial diversity of their consortia in a given habitat (Pakniker et al., 2009). The pH dependence of metal adsorption can largely be related to the type and ionic state of the functional group present on the bio sorbent and the type of metal species present in the solution (Pakniker et al., 2009). The study conducted by a selected tannery viz., Mario Jose using agricultural waste e.g. modified rice husk medium (MRHM) and modified sawdust medium (MSDM) in comparison with conventional medium potato dextrose medium (PDM) as shown in table 3, 4 and 5. Similar findings regarding the removal of chromium (VI) varied with alternation in pH with live growing fungi with increase in pH from 2-6 Rapport and Mutter, (1994). Thus, in contrast to removal by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* from contaminated effluent waste whereas increase in pH from 5-8.0 lead to elevated Cr^{6+} removal (Krauter et al., 1996). In this study, the changes due to pH fluctuation prior from weak acid to above neutrality as in the case of (MSDM), (MRHM) and weak acid to strong acid spotted on (PDM) respectively, showed the living mycelia mat condition to a maximum pH of base. On the availability of maximum binding sites for Cr^{6+} biosorption fungal cell walls, are negatively charged under alkaline pH condition and the cell walls chemical functional groups display a high affinity for metal ions in alkaline solution (Collins and Stotzky, 2009). The surface of adsorbent become highly protonated and favors the uptake of Cr^{6+} in anionic form under acidic to above neutrality. The degree of protonation and adsorption increase with increase in pH also showed that there is competition between hydroxyl and chromate ions for binding as the former being dominant species at above neutral pH values. Other literature review state that the different pH binding profiles for heavy metal ions could also be attributed to the nature of chemical interaction of each metal with microbial cell and are related to isoelectric point, there is a negative charge on the cells and the ionic state ligands (carboxyl, phosphate and amino groups) promotes reaction with the metal cations. As the pH is lowered as shown table 5 however, the overall surface charged on the cells becomes positive, which results in the inhibition of the approach of positively charged metal cations (Sag and Kutsal, 1995). *Aspergillus niger* removed Cr^{6+} under both acidic and alkaline condition (Lefebvre et al., 2007).

Figure 7. Picture Showing Mixed Culture of Filamentous Fungi (*Rhizopus nigrican*), *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *penicillium sp.* Isolated from Mario Jose Tannery Kano Using Base Medium

The above studies show *Rhizopus nigricans*, *Aspergillus niger* and mixed culture organisms appear to be more effective in biosorption of Cr⁶⁺ in effluent using modified agricultural waste in comparison with conventional ones. These above findings could also be attributed on the basis of development of suitable operational strategies for the removal of Cr (VI) from contaminated waste water.

Table1. Characterization of Fungi isolates from Tannery Effluent (MarioJose)

Isolates	Microscopic observations				
	Colony colours	Colony diameter	Conidiophore length (mm)	Conidia NM diameter	Conidia shape
<i>Aspergillum niger</i>	Black	1.50	3.25	3.48	Oval
<i>Rhizopus nigricians</i>	Brown	2.30	3.42	4.20	Globose
<i>Penicillium</i> sp	Green/blue	2.40	0.72	2.90	-
<i>Aspergillum flavus</i>	Greenish/green	1.40	3.24	3.20	Globose
<i>Candida</i> sp	Creamy milky	0.18	-	-	-

Key = - Not applicable

Table 2. Chromium Sulphate Tolerance Level by the Isolated Fungi sp Length of Mycelia (mm) at Different Concentration (%)

Isolates	00	0.1	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	4.0
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	32.80	28.25	16.50	12.83	11.21	10.30	10.0
<i>Rhizopus nigricians</i>	36.75	34.45	34.05	20.20	19.80	14.03	12.02
<i>Penicillium</i> sp	30.14	25.28	18.77	12.30	10.28	9.12	8.30
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	12.32	9.40	8.25	5.45	4.34	-	-
<i>Candida</i> sp	15.72	9.24	-	-	-	-	-

Key = - Not tolerant

Table 3. Chromium Remediation by Individual Filamentous Strain MRHM

Test organism	Initial Cr conc. mg/l	Cr conc.mg/l After 45days	Efficiency (%)	Temperature (°C)	PH Range
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	1.517	0.072	94.20	32	5.20-7.20
<i>Rhizopus nigricians</i>	1.517	0.067	88.45	32	5.20-7.80
<i>Penicillium</i> sp	1.517	0.730	84.20	32	5.20-7.40
<i>Mixed culture</i>	1.517	0.742	64.20	32	5.20-7.60

Table 4. Chromium Remediation by Individual Filamentous Strain MSDM

Test organism	Initial Cr conc. mg/l	Cr conc mg/l After 45days	Efficiency (%)	Temp °C	pH Range
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	1.517	0.934	94.20	32	5.20-7.50
<i>Rhizopus nigricians</i>	1.517	0.080	88.45	32	5.20-7.80
<i>Penicillium</i> sp	1.517	0.960	84.20	32	5.20-7.40
<i>Mixed Culture</i>	1.517	0.094	64.20	32	5.20-7.60

Table 5. Chromium Remediation by Individual Filamentous Strain PDM

Test organism	Initial Cr Conc. mg/l	Cr Conc. mg/l After 45days	Effluent %	Temp. 32°C	pH Range
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	1.517	1.301	94.20	32	5.20-4.50
<i>Rhizopus nigricans</i>	1.517	1.013	88.45	32	5.20-4.60
<i>Penicillium</i> sp	1.517	1.329	84.20	32	5.20-4.32
Mixed culture	1.517	1.384	64.20	32	5.20-4.00

Conclusion

The problem of hazardous waste containing chromium (VI) has become a major concern in the country. Proper treatment of tannery waste in the industry before discharge is extremely essential for public use especially for drinking and irrigation purpose. In this present investigation conducted, is to ameliorate chromium (VI) present in tannery waste water to barest level of permissible limit of 0.05mg/l by (WHO1998) from industrial waste for sustainability of microorganisms, plants as well as human life. Therefore, the used of locally available agricultural waste i.e. modified rice husk medium (MRHM) in combination with tannery effluent containing chromium ion varying volumes of sterile media using resistant or tolerant filamentous fungi viz., *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizopus nigricans* and *Penicillium* sp were used for bioremediation process.

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